

Dynamic Sales and Inventory System, and Customer Demands

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Abstract

Now a day it is very import for the vendors to keep tract information about their products or item so they can manage sales and inventory of a product. Generally the system of inventory depends upon the demand of a particular product. In this paper we arte discuss about how we can manage the dynamic sales and inventory by the different system.

Keywords: Demand, Dynamic Sales, Inventory.

1. Introduction

Dynamic sales and inventory system is a system that deals with the production of a goods or any item for selling and inventory. An inventory system combines desktop software, barcode scanners, barcode labels, and mobile devices to streamline the tracking of inventory (e.g. consumables, goods, SKUs, supplies, etc.) as product flows through a warehouse

environment. This could be a single stockroom or multiple warehouses spread across the country[asap system]. Dynamic Sales and Inventory System is a management system that keeps track about the sales and inventory of different items of a production and sales company. So that the company can take and review all the details about their item. In the twenty-first century, with the globalization of the markets, there has been a considerable increase in trade through-out the world. Firms produce, maintain and distribute goods on all continents.

quantity, price and other aspects that must be negotiated and set ahead of time for the entire planning horizon. This results in a stable demand stream at the seller (or manufacturer) and it ensures availability of the items for the buyer.[3]. For the proper management of dynamic sales and inventory system we also need some software that can make online or offline systems for electronically management of all data. Some software that is used to make project for this system. They are ASP.Net, VB.Net, Php and so on.

Customers demand products that must be supplied quickly and efficiently. [1]One of the concerns of the companies producing perishable products is to have an effective inventory management system to improve the customer service and provide competitive advantages in the current global marketplace.[2]In many industries, buyers diversify their procurement strategy in order to reduce component or raw material shortages, especially when the supply is tight (e.g., memory parts in the semiconductor industry). Buyers can set up long-term demand fulfillment contracts with the manufacturer. Such contractual agreements include the order

1.1 Objective

Time can be reducing by eliminating the duplicate data entries in different records. By managing the data in computer a lot of paper can be saved resulting in less wastage of natural resource. Many persons are involved in the malignance of data a single computer can replace them as the time is saved. Manpower is reduced and there is reduction in power this leads directly to reduction in overhead expenses.

1.2 Literature Review

According to S. Li, Y. He, and L. Chen,2017 In 2000, a fire occurred in a Philips semiconductor plant in New Mexico. The fire, which lasted for approximately ten minutes, severely impacted two of the world's largest mobile phone manufacturers in Europe. This event directly resulted in Ericsson's withdrawal from the mobile phone market. [4]So the vendors can only produce inventory of those product who having the actual market values. If we produce

those items that market values are already getting down by some reasons, then we can't properly stand or dynamically sale our products. For dynamic sales and inventory we also need to focus on inventory control systems.

According to A. Jalili Marand, H. Li, and A. Thorstenson, Inventory control and pricing are prominent representatives of operations and marketing aspects, respectively. For instance, blood bags are required for conducting cosmetic surgeries at hospitals, and cosmetic surgery demand is highly influenced by price[5].

So all the products is only need the actual demand by their customers then only the sales inventory system of that product can inventory that product.

According to J. Meissner and O. V. Senicheva, 2018, The dominant cause of mismatch between customer demand and a retailer's available stock is demand uncertainty. While modern information technologies offer possibilities to store big data and forecast the average demand rate quite accurately for groups of products, there are still markets in which demand uncertainty results in unsold inventories and loss of sales, reducing retailer profits. Companies usually use historical data for recent years and allocate their inventories across multiple regions based on the previous year's sales patterns. [6]

1.3 Present System

As we know manual systems are quite tedious, time consuming and less effective and inaccurate in comparison to the computerized system. We know that to maintain data into copy and memory is makes lots of confusion and paper work issue.

1.4 Proposed System

For the development of Dynamic Sales and Inventory system we are using here VB.net and to store data we are using SQL Server 2008. It makes possible to develop a stand alone project on Dynamic Sales and Inventory system for the vendors.

1.4.1 Snap Shot of a Project

Fig: Login Form

Fig: Progress Successful

Fig: MDI Form

Fig: Category Form

Fig: Product Details

Fig; Supplier Order

Fig: Supplier Detail

Fig: Customer Report

Fig: Searching Form

Fig: Product Report

Fig: Customer Order

Fig: Order Report

2. Methodology

2.1 VB.Net

NET (VB.NET) is a multi-paradigm, object oriented programming language, implemented on the .NET Framework. Microsoft launched VB.NET in 2002 as the successor to its original Visual Basic language. Although the “.NET” portion of the name was dropped in 2005, this article uses “Visual Basic [.NET]” to refer to all Visual Basic languages releases since 2002, in order to distinguish between them and the classic Visual Basic. Along with Visual C#, it is one of the two main languages targeting the .NET framework.

Microsoft’s integrated development environment (IDE) for developing in Visual Basic .NET language is Visual Studio. Most Visual Studio editions are commercial; the only exceptions are Visual Studio Express and Visual Studio Community, which are freeware. In addition, the .NET Framework SDK includes a freeware command-line compiler called vbc.exe. Mono also includes a command-line VB.NET compiler.

Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Visual_Basic_.NET

2.2 Microsoft SQL Server 2005

Microsoft SQL Server 2005 Express Edition has been designed with older Microsoft operating systems in mind. Offering bespoke data management options as well as the ability to enhance levels of performance, this bundle can be downloaded in the event that the original SQL copy was lost or otherwise corrupted. This is the official software package offered by Microsoft. Originally published in 2005, Microsoft SQL Server 2005 Express Edition provides the user with all of the most important tools to better manage his or her system. As the name may already suggest, this bundle can be used with older versions of Microsoft such as Microsoft XP and Microsoft 2000. Some core processes include advanced data protection, the better management of online applications and

superior data storage solutions. This software can come in quite handy if a system seems to be running poorly.

Source: <https://microsoft-sql-server-2005-express-edition.en.softonic.com/#app-softonic-review>

2.3 HTML

HTML (Hypertext Markup Language) is the set of markup symbols or codes inserted in a file intended for display on a World Wide Web browser page. The markup tells the Web browser how to display a Web page’s words and images for the user. Each individual markup code is referred to as an element (but many people also refer to it as a tag). Some elements come in pairs that indicate when some display effect is to begin and when it is to end.

Source: <https://searchmicroservices.techtarget.com>

2.4 CSS

CSS stands for “Cascading Style Sheet.” Cascading style sheets are used to format the layout of Web pages. They can be used to define text styles, table sizes, and other aspects of Web pages that previously could only be defined in a page’s HTML.

CSS helps Web developers create a uniform look across several pages of a Web site. Instead of defining the style of each table and each block of text within a page’s HTML, commonly used styles need to be defined only once in a CSS document.

Source: <https://techterms.com/definition/css>

2.5 Feasibility Study

A feasibility study is an analysis of how successfully a project can be completed, accounting for factors that affect it such as economic, technological, legal and scheduling factors. Project managers use feasibility studies to determine potential positive and negative outcomes of a project before investing a considerable amount of time and money into it.

Source: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/feasibility-study.asp>

Result

In our project, I have arranged different section related to "Sales and Investors" in much more coordinated and logical manner. This project intended to resolve the problem existing in the manual system. The project into various sections that present a clear picture of the system. Such section that can be used to extent and solidified his or her knowledge about the system. Simplicity is more importance while designing. All possible aspects of the system are taken into consideration. User friendliness is aimed in this project. It is hope that project may be useful for the user.

Conclusion

We are conclude that the concept dynamic sales and inventory system can be possible only if the vendors perfectly know about the market values of a particular product, know the valid and scenario of a product price and the most important demand of a goods or many item by the customer. For Dynamic sales and inventory Systems we need a proper software that can handle real time demand and inventory problems. This system is beneficial for the vendors and sales and inventory industry so they can manage their sales and inventory systems according to the public demand.

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